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THE KEY ASPECTS OF CRITICAL THINKING IN TEACHER'S COMPETENCE IN LINGUA-COACHING APPROACH

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Annotation: This article defines about the competence in teaching that refers to the knowledge, skills, and abilities that teachers possess to effectively carry out their responsibilities. It includes subject matter expertise, pedagogical knowledge, instructional strategies, classroom management skills, assessment techniques, communication skills, adaptability, cultural sensitivity, and the ability to create a positive learning environment. Motivation is an essential component of competence and refers to the ability to make logical conclusions and decisions through a process of analyzing and evaluating information.

Key words: Teacher Competence, Resistance, Motivation, Problem solving, Critical thinking

ВАЖНОСТЬ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЯ В ЛИНГВО- КОУЧИНГОВОМ ПОДХОДЕ

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Аннотация: В этой статье дается определение компетентности в преподавании, которая относится к знаниям, навыкам и умениям, которыми обладают учителя для эффективного выполнения своих обязанностей. Она включает в себя знания в предметной области, педагогические знания, стратегии обучения, навыки управления классом, методы оценки, коммуникативные навыки, адаптивность, культурную восприимчивость и способность создавать позитивную учебную среду. Мотивация является важным компонентом компетентности и относится к способности делать логические выводы и принимать решения в процессе анализа и оценки информации.

Ключевые слова: Компетентность учителя, Сопротивление, Мотивация, Решение проблем.

Competences emphasize what the instructions have to accomplish during the lessons. The term ‘**competence**’ is derived from Latin “*competentia*” which means the aggregate of the people’s personal qualities conditioned by the experience of their activity in a certain social sphere.

Teacher competence refers to the knowledge, skills, and abilities that teachers possess in order to effectively carry out their teaching responsibilities. It encompasses a wide range of qualities and competencies that are required for successful teaching. These may include subject matter expertise, pedagogical knowledge, instructional strategies, classroom management skills, assessment and evaluation techniques, communication and interpersonal skills, adaptability and flexibility, cultural sensitivity, and the ability to create a positive learning environment.

A competent teacher is not only knowledgeable in their subject area but also has the ability to effectively convey that knowledge to students using appropriate teaching methods. They understand how students learn best and are capable of adapting their instruction to meet diverse learning needs. Additionally, a competent teacher possesses strong classroom management skills to maintain an orderly and productive learning environment.

Competence also extends beyond the classroom. A competent teacher is committed to continuous professional development by staying updated with current research and best practices in education. They are reflective practitioners who constantly evaluate and refine their teaching methods based on student feedback and performance data.

Furthermore, teacher competence includes effective communication with students, parents, colleagues, and other stakeholders involved in the education process. It involves building relationships with students based on trust and respect while fostering a supportive learning community within the classroom.

The first studies on the term “competence” found in Webster’s dictionary appeared approximately in 1956 and it is generally understood to mean “the ability to do something successfully and efficiently”[1]. However, the period of its application from theory to practice in education is relatively small. The term “competence” was substituted with the terminology “literacy”, which has been used for a long time, although this concept was defined and interpreted in different ways. As a result, the limited understanding of literacy was recognized as a concept that includes only the abilities to read and write. In many cases, literacy began to co-relate with the concept of ‘basic skills’ comprising listening,

speaking, reading, writing, skills in mathematics, working with information, and etc.

It is considered that the term “competence” was initially introduced by R.White in 1959 in the article “Motivation reconsidered: The concept of competence”[2]. Several scholars have attempted various viewpoints to define the term “competence” initially in the field of business. In accordance with Tracey Weiss, leaders typically struggle ineffectually not because they have technical abilities or knowledge of their job, but rather they have shortcomings in competence.

Critical thinking. According to D. Halpern in the book “Psychology of Critical Thinking”, critical thinking is the ability to make up logical conclusions and take unanimous decisions. Furthermore, it is considered to be a process, not only a result. Critical thinking remains passive when the activity of apprehending new concepts given by others in the process is accepted. As a result, critical thinking will be active or it will start when the lingua-coach begins analyzing, examining or evaluating the newly accepted concepts.

Other scientists like Richard Paul and Linda Edler interpret critical thinking as “giving a new shape to thinking by understanding its strengths and weaknesses; the ability and desire to objectively evaluate the basis of well-proven causes, and to continue to think, no matter what, critical thinking is not purely negative thinking”[18]. Consequently, critical thinking is a frame of reference or idea the focal point of which are the conclusions and evaluations on the basis of analysis of happenings, things and events.

Problem-solving is one of the tedious and arduous skill in teachers’ competence. According to D. Jonassen a problem defined as “an unknown entity in some situation; finding or solving for the unknown must have some social, cultural, or intellectual value”[19]. And the problem-solving is a goal-oriented step that involves manipulating and creating problems as a mental example. In addition, problem-solving may involve addressing issues such as grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, cultural differences, or other factors that can impact language proficiency.

The necessary part of problem solving for instructors is to be able to define and present the problem and offer its solutions. For instance, the researcher C.Berkenkotter states, “A writer is a problem solver of a particular kind. Writers’ ‘solutions’ will be determined by how they frame their problems, the goals they set for themselves, and the means or plans they adopt for achieving those goals”[20]. Thus, in lingua-coaching instructors should assist their students in

comprehending and uniting into the research of their field by assigning short articles and guiding them through the practice of rhetorical devices. These actions provide the learners with various opportunities to specify their writing skills.

Motivating in lingua-coaching plays a dominating role. The lingua-coach has the tools that help make English as a part of a student's life and form a positive attitude toward the language. Learning English should not be limited to sessions, lessons or consultations. A coach can inspire a student to independently search for information in the language, watch TV shows, instructional videos, read articles and then share it with the teacher. In motivation, it is essential to highlight **moral support, time and control** as a part of a lingua-coach competence.

Moral support

The functions of a lingua-coach are not limited to a simple explanation of the teaching material. In fact, limited beliefs and psychological blocks of the student cause the challenges in comprehending and applying a foreign language. The coach's task is to help student work through and overcome them. Moral support is crucial in motivation because it helps individuals feel encouraged and validated. When someone feels valued and supported, they are more likely to stay motivated and focused on their goals. A lingua-coach who can provide moral support by being a positive role model, offering praise and constructive feedback can help individuals maintain their motivation.

Time

Time is also an essential aspect of motivation because people often struggle to find the time to work towards their goals. A lingua-coach who understands the importance of time management can help individuals prioritize their tasks and find ways to make time for language learning. However, usually learners' complain about their insufficient of time and laziness in learning English. Indeed, they have time, but no desire. Thus, lingua-coach helps find inner motivation and inspiration of using English and inscribe it in their daily life.

Control

Control is another important factor in motivation because individuals need to feel like they have some control over the process. In lingua-coaching control is one of the ways of a positive motivation. As a proverb says, "never climbed, never fell", we learn from our mistakes. It is necessary and normal to make mistakes. The task of a coach is to analyze the errors of the learners and assist them to work at as well as the basis of self-control.

To conclude, teacher competence is a comprehensive combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors that enable teachers to effectively

facilitate student learning and growth. It plays a central role in providing high-quality education and positively impacting students' academic achievement and overall development. Lingua-coaching has been defined as a reflection of a changing relationship between the teacher and the students. It is apparent that lingua-coaching can be the element of the lesson, for example, setting the aim or emerging the crisis situations including frustration or lack of motivation. The competences of a professional lingua-coach listed above can be considered as recommendations for building interaction with students, which entirely fit into the framework of a personality-oriented approach to learning. Moreover, the competences allow for the individualization of the pedagogical and educational process. Hence, lingua-coaching as a pedagogical technology is widely in demand within the framework of individual classes. Teacher competence is critical for successful implementation of lingua-coaching approach. Teachers who possess strong theoretical knowledge of this approach combined with excellent linguistic proficiency, interpersonal skills and reflective practice can create an effective learning environment where learners can develop their communication competence through authentic interaction with others. In addition, the incorporation of lingua-coaching in a group setting can prove advantageous. The lingua-coach can foster group conversations, motivate active involvement, and offer personalized assistance to every learner. This teaching methodology promotes a favorable learning atmosphere where students feel at ease and self-assured in their abilities.

The list of used literature

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